

IMPLEMENTATION OF HIDDEN CURRICULUM IN ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION (CASE STUDY: PONDOK PESANTREN HIDAYATULLAH BALIKPAPAN)

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Abstract

This study aims to know about how the implementation of hidden curriculum in environmental education in Pondok Pesantren Hidayatullah Balikpapan. This research uses eco pesantren theory. The method used is qualitative research method with data collection through field observation, documentation, literature study, and interview. This study concludes that first, the results of the study illustrate that environmental education at Pondok Pesantren Hidayatullah Balikpapan is already running. Second, the implementation of the hidden curriculum in environmental education is focused on direct implementation activities by practicing what has been taught in the boarding school environment. Third, the implications of the existence of the hidden curriculum of environmental education make santri have good acts in preserving the environment.

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1. Introduction

Environmental education is an educational program that aims to change human attitudes and behavior in order to reproduce rationally, maintain the environment, and be responsible for the quality of life now and in the future through the education process ¹ Environmental coping strategies should start in education, namely education Environment. Likewise in the education curriculum that is directly related to the implementation of subject matter in real action, ², in this case I discuss the hidden curriculum.

Through education, someone will get a lot of experience. education does not only occur in pesantren, wherever education can also be obtained. But, when talking about education, surely what is in mind is education in pesantren. Talking about education, of course, can not be separated from how the results or output of the education. One element of education that plays a role in determining the quality of graduates is the curriculum. The elements of the hidden curriculum possessed in schools are values, beliefs, attitudes, and norms and values that are an important part of school functions, ceremonies and the quality of interpersonal communication³

The curriculum is a written plan about abilities that must be possessed based on national standards, material that needs to be learned and learning experiences that must be undertaken to achieve these abilities,

¹ Fachruddin, Suaedi. Pembelajaran Pendidikan Lingkungan Hidup. Bogor: *IPB Press*, 2016.

² Mohammad Takdir, Modernisasi Kurikulum Pesantren, Yogyakarta: *Ircisod*, 2018.

³ Cubukcu, Zuhail. "The Effect of Hidden Curriculum on Character Education Process of Primary School Students", *Journal Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 2012, Vol.12 No. 2 p 1526-1534

and evaluations that need to be done to determine the level of achievement of students' abilities, as well as a set of rules relating to students' learning experiences in develops his potential in certain education units.⁴ Whenever talking about change, the aim is certainly a change in curriculum. In Indonesia itself, it has undergone several changes in curriculum. Hidden curriculum involves the fact that the educational environment includes how children are treated as learners to communicate with human expectations and views, and form an intrinsic part of children's learning

An institution, including a pesantren, certainly has a curriculum, especially those related to the environment. He hopes that his students will be faithful and fearful people with competitive and comparative advantages. They are expected to have a balance between physical and spiritual strength and high sensitivity or in other words, it is expected that they will be cognitively intelligent students and must also have a high sense of responsibility towards the environment, maintain and preserve it and emphasize the use and management of natural resources for sustainable development and development. In order to achieve this goal, some pesantren create curriculum that is not owned by pesantren in general, more precisely Hidden Curriculum, which is an additional curriculum that is not contained in the formal curriculum, whose existence is an extension of the curriculum contained in the formal curriculum. The hidden curriculum is capable of influencing changes in students' values, perceptions and behavior. An educational institution certainly has the desired goal. To achieve this goal the school will create a curriculum that is not in school in general, namely the hidden curriculum..⁵

It is expected that the implementation of Hidden Curriculum in the environment which emphasizes students to spiritual attitudes or social attitudes towards the environment by preserving and preserving it and will reduce the damage to environmental damage that has already occurred in Indonesia and the utilization and management of natural resources for development and continuation of sustainable development. Thus, it is hoped that students who are good moral and always include their religion in every deed can be realized.

2. Research Methodology

This study includes qualitative research which means that the data collected comes from interview scripts, personal documents, memo notes, field notes and other official documents. The purpose of this study is to describe the empirical reality behind the phenomenon in depth, detail and complete. Sources of data from this study come from primary data and secondary data. Primary data uses data in the form of observations, interviews and questionnaires to get direct information about the concept of pesantren-based environmental management. Secondary data used to strengthen the findings and supplement the information collected through direct interviews with the pesantren came from reading sources and various other sources consisting of books, journals and official documents from various agencies. In addition, attachments from official bodies such as ministry data, results of studies, theses, dissertations, historical studies and so forth. Data collection techniques used in the form of direct observation, interviews, documentation and data analysis. This observation is used for research that has been planned systematically on the concept of pesantren-based environmental management . Next is the interview that was asked directly to the figures at the boarding school. Then the documentation in the form of small notes from the author's observations,

⁴ Oemar Hamalik, Manajemen Pengembangan kurikulum, Bandung: *PT Remaja Rosdakarya*, 2010.

⁵ Khairun Nisa, "Hidden Curriculum : Upaya Peningkatan Kecerdasan Spritual Siswa", *Jurnal Lentera Pendidikan*, Vol.,12 NO.1 (June, 2009) 72-86.

photographs and recordings of activities at the boarding school and its facilities and infrastructure. Data analysis that is done after using the data collection technique above is processing and analyzing the data using descriptive-qualitative analysis.

3. Result and Discussion

Based on the description of the implementation of the hidden curriculum based on environmental education, here are the findings of the hidden curriculum based on environmental education at Pesantren Hidayatullah Balikpapan which is effective in environmental conservation efforts:

3.1 Implementation of Hidden Curriculum in Environmental Education

The location of the boarding school is on the equator and on the coast makes the weather there quite hot. The temperature there ranges from 31-35 ° C during the day and 28-32 ° C at night. Even frequent forest fires and difficulties in getting clean water during a long dry season. In implementing Hidden Curriculum, assistance and cooperation from various parties, both the head of the pesantren, education and the learning environment are needed. The head of the Pesantren has a major role in determining the policies that will be applied in pesantren. Whereas education / teacher has the duty to deliver policies that have been established by the clerics to students with strategies and methods that teachers have so that students can walk in accordance with established policies and vision, mission and goals of pesantren can be implemented properly related to Hidden Curriculum at Pondok Pesantren Hidayatullah Balikpapan, the head of the Islamic boarding school, KH Zainuddin Musaddad in collaboration with education / teachers has implemented several programs including:

First, the environmental cleanliness ticket is \pm 200 hectares

When starting the Pesantren Hidayatullah Balikpapan there was a unique policy when the acceptance of new students, namely the boarding school entrance test did not use religious or Arabic language tests as in general, but prospective students were assigned to hoe the lakes and clean up the dirt in the lake for 40 days⁶ Pesantren this is on the island of Kalimantan and also on the coast which covers almost 200 hectares. One important aspect in environmental management of Islamic-based Islamic boarding schools according to Fachruddin Mangunjaya is the policy in Islamic boarding schools. The policy of Islamic boarding schools is run one of them with an environmental foundation. The policy of Islamic boarding schools must have basic norms and basic principles of ethnics such as matters concerning worship (Rub'u al-ibadat), social matters (Rub'u al-muamalat), matters of kinship (rub'ul al- munakahat), and the matter of the application of sanctions (rub'ul al-jinayat). The vision is reflected in the two commitments of structuring boarding school complex land, namely: first, arranged as an arena of education with a healthy environment, secondly, arranged as an educational institution based on the spirit of integrated economic independence.

Second, Periodic Green Plant Planting

The vision of environmentally friendly Islamic boarding schools is also supported by the ideals of the founding of Islamic boarding schools namely KH Ahmad Said and the four other founders who want land use in Gunung Tembak as a habitable place and as an educational institution capable of producing Islamic leaders who are useful in the community. There are several principles that encourage the birth of the cottage vision, namely scientific principles, natural

⁶ Ahmad Damanik,. Jejak Dakwah Sang Perintis. Hidayatullah, (April, 2015) 48-49.

principles and Islamic principles. Of these three principles, it was developed to become the vision of Islamic boarding schools that is to become an excellent, trustworthy and independent Islamic education institution.

The realization of this vision can be seen from the rules of the boarding school which contains many regulations relating to the environment. Such as punishment for planting trees if students make mistakes, prohibiting cutting trees, learning environmental management in the hidden curriculum of Islamic boarding schools, distribution of funds for Islamic boarding schools for the surrounding environment and others.⁷

Third, Addressing and Managing Natural Disasters

Environmental issues or environmental degradation can be interpreted as a decrease in environmental quality caused by development activities characterized by a lack of proper functioning of environmental components as appropriate⁸ Efforts to protect and manage the environment in this Hidayatullah Pesantren is a training of nature lovers students initiated by students MA and also students .. Where the students are equipped with the ability to cope with emergencies or disasters.

The interesting thing here is that in the event of a disaster around the Islamic boarding school, it is the students who are the front guard in carrying out rescue and coping activities. The last time the students were directly involved in suppressing peatland fires that occurred in the Balikpapan area. That way the students can play a direct role in improving environmental conditions, especially during a disaster. And most importantly students know how important it is to protect the environment. Because if the disaster has come then the effect will be very large and also fatal.

This is in line with the vision of the pesantren founder who wants students to learn directly from nature. Through practice and going directly to the field, not with theory or learning in the classroom. Because if the nature directly teaches the santri will immediately get the effect, whether positive or negative. In addition, by prioritizing participatory-based activities, the santri dis. Some of the above activities are Hidden Curriculum activities in environmental education that can support the attitude of responsibility and care of students towards their environment.

The methods used are as follows:

First, the method of fostering environmental awareness

Islamic Boarding Schools certainly want their students to be personal who love the environment. With this environment-based pesantren, it is hoped that students can have behaviors that are in accordance with Islamic teachings that love the environment.¹⁴ In addition, in a child's soul that has been taught about the environment since childhood, it will be guided and fostered in an environment-based pesantren. In this way, santri awareness of the environment will emerge and can develop according to what the pesantren expected.

Second, Exemplary Method

⁷ Interview with the leader of Pondok Pesantren Hidayatullah Balikpapan, Ustadz Zainuddin Musaddad, "Latar Belakang Pondok Pesantren Hidayatullah". (2017, Agustus 9). (A. Gunawan, & M. Firdaus, *Interviewer*)

⁸ Aulia, Rihlah Nur, Moh Firdaus, Ade Gunawan, dan Dian Elvira. "Konsep Ecodesantren dalam Menjawab Degradasi Lingkungan." Seminar Nasional Dalam Rangka Dies Natalis ke-53 UNJ. Jakarta : *Laboratorium Sosial Politik Press UNJ*, 2017. 551-560.

Kyai / Ustadz is the most important example for santri. We know that santri are more likely to imitate what is done by the cleric. So in order to achieve the objectives of the application of Hidden Curriculum, a credible and authoritative cleric is needed, specifically the cleric who introduces the importance of protecting the environment, and all education in general. In learning both inside and outside the pesantren environment, education must truly maintain an attitude. In the application of Hidden Curriculum, the behavior of all education at the Pesantren Hidayatullah Balikpapan must be maintained so that the atmosphere in the pesantren is good so that students will be more positive.

Third, habituation method

Habit becomes important in changing the behavior of santri to be better or even worse. Each student has a different family character and background. For example, students who have a bad background and have a bad attitude, for example, like carelessly littering, polluting the environment, etc. it could be that he would bring this attitude at the pesantren because it had become a habit at home. Therefore education must slowly change the habits of such students to a better direction. With the habit of implementing actions that are in accordance with religious teachings, it is hoped that santri will be better.

3.2 Implications for implementing the Hidden Curriculum in environmental education at Pondok Hidayatullah Pesantren Balikpapan

The application of Hidden Curriculum on Environmental Education at Pesantren Hidayatullah Balikpapan is expected to be a shield for students and can facilitate changes in good attitudes towards the environment of the students so that Islamic nuances of Hidden Curriculum are applied, so that santri always have a high caring attitude towards the environment. The implications expected from the Hidden Curriculum are:

First, the environmental cleanliness ticket is \pm 200 hectares

This activity is a routine activity every week that is conducted every week by all elements of the pesantren, ranging from kyai, clerics, santri, and the surrounding community in cleaning the environment of the hidayatullah balikpapan pesantren which covers approximately \pm 200 hectares. This activity includes cleaning rice fields, artificial lakes, oil palm plantations, pesantren buildings and so on. This activity is expected that the behavior and care of students can be maintained in their environment, so that they become caring and love their environment. Indicators of their success can be seen from. Their concern in preserving the environment. If students have better attitude changes, this means that the application of the Hidden Curriculum for Environmental Education has a positive impact on students.

Second, Periodic Green Plant Planting

This activity is a periodic activity which includes the obligation of new students to accept a tree and take care of him until he graduated, also in the form of punishment for planting trees for students who violate pesantren regulations. This activity is expected that the behavior and concern of students towards the beauty of the environment, cool and beautiful plants and trees, so they become concerned in preserving the environment. Indicators of their success can be seen from. Their concern in preserving the environment. If students have better attitude changes, this means that the application of the Hidden Curriculum for Environmental Education has a positive impact on students.

Third, Addressing and Managing Natural Disasters

This activity is an impromptu activity, but has been prepared in advance in handling and handling natural disasters, one of which is formed by a community of nature lovers in dealing with natural disasters such as landslides, floods and forest fires that occur at any time in the Pesantren Hidayatullah Balikpapan or surrounding areas. Therefore, the task force was formed as an active participation in Islamic boarding schools in helping to deal with the equatorial environmental problems, namely forest fires. One of the important roles of the task force was to help overcome peatland fires in Balikpapan some time ago⁹ Answering environmental degradation requires the existence of an ecological concept that is able to solve the problem of environmental degradation with the basic concept is to change the mindset of humans towards their environment..¹⁰. This activity is expected that the sensitivity of santri towards the surrounding environment can be formed, so that they become sensitive in a disaster that will happen at any time. Indicators of their success can be seen from. their sensitivity in tackling environmental disasters. If students have better attitude changes, this means that the application of the Hidden Curriculum for Environmental Education has a positive impact on students.

4. Conclusion

This study concludes that first the results of the study illustrate that environmental education at the Pesantren Hidayatullah Balikpapan is already underway. Second, the implementation of the hidden curriculum in environmental education is focused on the activities of direct implementation by practicing what has been taught in the boarding school environment. Third, the implications of the hidden curriculum of environmental education make students have good character in preserving their environment.

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⁹ Interview with representatives of curriculum fields Pondok Pesantren Hidayatullah Balikpapan, Ustadz Paryadi,, Kurikulum dan Pengkaderan Pondok Pesantren Hidayatullah Balikpapan, (2017, Agustus 7).. (A. Gunawan, & M. Firdaus, *Interviewer*)

¹⁰ Aulia, Rihlah Nur, Moh Firdaus, Ade Gunawan, dan Dian Elvira. "Konsep Ecodesantren dalam Menjawab Degradasi Lingkungan." Seminar Nasional Dalam Rangka Dies Natalis ke-53 UNJ. Jakarta : Laboratorium Sosial Politik Press UNJ, 2017. 551-560.

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